

**THERAPEUTIC EVALUATION OF SIDDHAR YOGIC MUDRAS (HAND GESTURES) FOR
STRESS MANAGEMENT: A CASE SERIES**

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ABSTRACT

Siddhar Yogam is a meticulous wing of Siddha System of medicine. It deals with physical, mental and spiritual development strengthening gross body, subtle body and causal body. Siddha system relies on Pancha Bootham theory. Mudras are subtle science involving geometry and circuitry of the body which deepens awareness and concentration. It is an essential tool to focus mind and facilitate energy flow within body. Mind and body are benefitted by hand gestures by activating specific energy in body. It connects inner self leading to inner peace and tranquility through altering mood, attitude, perception. This clinical trial aims to peer assessment of the therapeutic effect of Siddhar Yogic Mudras for Stress management through PSS-10 scale (Personalized Stress Scale). Chin mudra, Chinmay mudra, Shangu mudra, Kamala mudra and Anjali mudra are employed to manage stress. This observational study has been carried out in Out Patient Department of Siddhar Yoga Maruthuvam department, Government Siddha Medical College and Hospital, Palayamkottai. This Case series involves sample size of 15 participants using the Non-randomised Judgemental sampling method. These 5 mudras have been advised to study participants for a period of 45 days. The aim of this study is to document the stress management through Siddhar Yogic Mudra regimen. In this study, 15 study participants were followed up for 45 days for 6 sitting and PSS-10 assessment has been noted and documented as a case series in this paper. The outcome of the study indicates that there was a significant reduction in clinical conditions as well as notable changes in before and after treatment PSS scoring among the study participants.

KEYWORDS: Siddhar Yogam, Mudra Therapy, Stress Management, Subtle Science, PSS-10 scale.

INTRODUCTION

Siddha medicine is a principle of medical methods that treats & prevents diseases with disproportionate values of vatham, pitham and kabam using internal and external medication. It strengthens not only the gross body but also the subtle body. Ashtanga yogam (i.e. Iyamam, Niyamam and Asanam) plays a major role in mending the subtle body.

Asanam encompasses Mudras as per which each of our fingers represents each boodham (Ring finger - Earth, little finger- Water, Thumb finger - Fire, Index finger - Air and Middle finger -Space). Diseases occur in our body when the equilibrium of pancha boodhams alters in the body. Mudras balance the impaired ratio of pancha boodhams in body.

The word 'Mudra' literally means seal. It has a number of different connotations in yoga, which include bandhas (locks) and meditation practices. Mudras are hand gestures in which the fingers are related to different types

of energies, and when they are brought together in specific ways, they produce subtle effects.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Stress is defined as state of mental tension caused by a difficult situation. Many activities in daily life cause stress to people. In Siddha medicine stress is caused by pitham imbalance in the body. Stress affects both mind and body. When stress increases, various physical and mental health problems occur (like Depression, Bipolar disorder, Hypertension etc.). This is explained in our siddha literature Yugi vaidhya chinthamani 800.

“Maruvumē pulippuraip puvarppu miñcal
mañatilē tukkañka ļaṭaitalālum
neruvumē neruppuveyil kōpat tañnil
nittiraitā nillāmal viļittirukkum”

MUDRA (HAND GESTURES)

Hand Gestures influence physiological function by impacting nervous system and promote relaxation. It

balances energy flow within body, stimulating specific nerve endings and influencing brain activity. It activates parasympathetic nervous system, which relaxes and reduces body's stress response. It influences the flow of prana (vital energy) through the body. By stimulating specific points on hands, Mudras unblock and balance energy. It helps recoup lost vitality and focus their minds. Mudras increase energy and blood circulation to different parts of brain, vital nerve junctions and glands. Siddhars mapped out hand areas & their associated reflexes that relate to different areas of body and brain. Mudras apply tension to nerves which form the psycho neural circuits and help in balancing five basic elements.

Mudras can help balance the flow of energy through the nadis that nourish our internal organs. They can also be performed to achieve specific states of consciousness. They also help eliminate negative thought forms and aid mood elevation. It must be practiced with the spine and head erect in position. The eyes are focused downward toward the nostrils or at the Sun centre between the eyebrows to activate the third eye.

By the practice of Mudras, a connection is developed with the patterns in the brain that influences the unconscious reflexes in the different areas. The internal energy is balanced and redirected, creating an impact on the sensory organs, glands, tendons and veins.

BENIFITS OF MUDRAS

- Mudras stimulate brain and strengthens nervous system.
- It promotes interoceptive awareness by enhancing brain's ability to sense internal bodily states.
- It increases cognitive function by altering brain wave patterns.
- It influences the flow of prana through the body's energy channels (Naadi).
- It actively stimulates sensorimotor circuit.
- Mudras can cure almost any ailment from simple earache to heart attack.
- Mudras help in Kundalini Yoga to awaken the cosmic energy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. STUDY TYPE

Observational study.

B. STUDY DESIGN

Descriptive study - Case series.

C. STUDY PLACE

Out Patient Department, Department of Siddhar Yoga Maruthuvam, Government Siddha Medical College & Hospital, Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli, Tamil nadu.

D. STUDY PERIOD

4 Months.

E. SAMPLE SIZE

15 participants.

F. SAMPLING METHOD

Non Randomised Sampling (Judgement)

G. DURATION OF TREATMENT

45 days.

H. INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Age – 18 - 60 years.
- Sex : Male and Female
- PSS score upto 35
- If any 3 of the following symptoms of Stress are present, the participants will be included for the study.
 - ❖ Crying spells or bursts of anger
 - ❖ Difficulty in eating
 - ❖ Losing interest in daily activities
 - ❖ Increasing physical distress symptoms such as headaches or stomach pains
 - ❖ Fatigue
 - ❖ Feeling guilty, helpless, or hopeless
 - ❖ Insomnia
 - ❖ Avoiding family and friends

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- H/o Trauma in the Head
- Psychiatric disease
- Pregnant women
- History of Cardiac disorders
- PSS score more than 35
- Any other serious systemic illness

WITHDRAWAL CRITERIA

- Poor participant compliance and defaulters for 15 days.
- Participant unwilling to continue during clinical trial.
- Occurrence of any serious illness.
- Participants those who are unable to perform mudras.
- Increased in severity of symptoms during the study.

METHOD OF APPROACH

PSS - 10 Scale of Questionnaires.

5. DATA COLLECTION

INFORMATION COLLECTED

Information such as patient's personal details, medical histories and duration of illness has been collected.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis is carried out through Microsoft Excel and SPSS Software for logical error and manually cross checked for data entry error.

6. HUMAN PARTICIPATION PROCEDURE

The study involves human participants with intervention of Mudra. Participants are purely recruited based on primary data collection through Personalized Stress scale. Thereby voluntary willingness has been acquired through informed consent document and considered to participate in this study. The study is conducted only after getting the informed consent from the study participants.

8) METHOD OF APPROACH

MUDRA THERAPY

Total timing - 35 - 40 minutes

1. Chin mudra - 7 minutes
2. Chinmay mudra - 7 minutes
3. Shangu mudra - 7 minutes
4. Kamala mudra - 7 minutes
5. Anjali mudra - 7 minutes

Relaxation in between mudras is 1 minute ($5 \times 1 = 5$ Minutes)

GENERAL TERMS OF MUDRA PRACTICE

Choose a clean, well-ventilated surrounding. Each mudra works best in each asana. However, padmasanam or sukasanam or sitting in a reclined position, is sufficient. It is good to sit upright with the neck and spine straight. Mudras should be done on an empty stomach and only after 2 hours of eating.

1) CHIN MUDRA

- The tip of the thumb and the tip of the index finger should be brought together.
- The other fingers should be stretched loosely.
- Breathe in and out in that position.

2) CHINMAY MUDRA

- The tip of the thumb and the tip of the index finger should be brought together
- The other fingers should be folded and touched in the middle of the palm.
- Breathe in and out in that position.

3) SHANGU MUDRA

- Place the thumb of the left hand in the palm of the right hand and close it tightly with the four fingers of the right hand.
- The right hand should touch the tip of the thumb and the left hand with the middle finger.
- The other fingers of the left hand should also touch the thumb.
- Breathe in and out in that position.

4) KAMALA MUDRA

- Hold both fingers vertically. Bring the bottoms of both palms together.
- The tips of the thumbs and little fingers of the seats should touch each other (as shown in the picture).
- Hold the other fingers apart.
- Now the hands will look like a blooming lotus.
- Breathe in and out in that position.

5) ANJALI MUDRA

- Anjali mudra is how we place our hands in salutation.
- That is, the hands should not fluctuate up and down.
- There should be no space between the two hands.
- It should be at right level and at the right pressure
- Breathe in and out in that position.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION**DETAILS OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS**

SI NO	OP NO	AGE	SEX	DATE
1	58099	25	MALE	1-7-2024
2	66724	27	MALE	28/07/2024
3	2346	49	FEMALE	15/07/2024
4	66192	38	MALE	26/07/2024
5	59267	24	MALE	4-7-2024
6	73555	22	FEMALE	9-8-2024
7	73556	21	FEMALE	9-8-2024
8	70139	20	MALE	9-8-2024
9	73557	19	FEMALE	9-8-2024
10	70140	20	MALE	9-8-2024
11	76413	23	MALE	9-8-2024
12	76414	19	FEMALE	9-8-2024
13	76410	20	FEMALE	9-8-2024
14	76411	19	FEMALE	9-8-2024
15	75566	19	FEMALE	9-8-2024

AGE DISTRIBUTION**Fig. 9.1 Age Distribution.**

Out of 15 Participants, as shown in Fig.9.1, from the percentage of age distribution interpretation, 27% of Participants come under the age group of below 20 years, 60% of Participants come under the age group of 20 - 30 years, 7% of Participants come under the age group of 30-40 years and 7% of Participants come under the age group of 40 - 50 years.

Out of 15 Participants, as shown in Fig.9.1, from the age distribution interpretation, 4 Participants come under the age group of below 20 years, 9 Participants come under the age group of 20 - 30 years, 1 Participant comes under the age group of 30-40 years and 1 Participant comes under the age group of 40 - 50 years.

9.2 GENDER DISTRIBUTION**Fig. 9.2: Gender Distribution.**

Out of 15 Participants, as shown in Fig.9.2, from the percentage of gender distribution interpretation, 47% of Participants come under the male gender and 53% of Participants come under the female gender.

Out of 15 Participants, as shown in Fig. 9.2, from the gender distribution interpretation, 7 Participants are Male and 8 Participants are female.

9.3 OCCUPATION DISTRIBUTION**Fig. 9.3: Occupation Distribution.**

Out of 15 Participants, as shown in Fig.9.3, from the percentage of occupation distribution interpretation, 67% of Participants are Students, 20% of Participants are Daily Wages and 13% of Participants are House Wife.

Out of 15 Participants, as shown in Fig. 9.3, from the occupation distribution interpretation, 10 Participants are Students, 2 Participants are House Wife and 3 Participants are Daily Wages.

9.4 SCORING OF PSS - 10 SCALE BEFORE AND AFTER TREATMENT

S. NO	OP NO	BEFORE TREATMENT		AFTER TREATMENT	
		SCORE / PERRCENTAGE	SCORE / PERRCENTAGE	SCORE / PERRCENTAGE	SCORE / PERRCENTAGE
1	58099	23	57.5%	14	35%
2	66724	24	60%	16	40%
3	2346	26	65%	18	45%
4	66192	23	57.5%	16	40%
5	59267	22	55%	18	45%
6	73555	19	47.5%	15	37.5%
7	73556	25	62.5 %	17	42.5%
8	70139	30	75%	23	57.5%
9	73557	28	70%	24	60%
10	70140	28	70%	23	57.5%
11	76413	20	50%	16	40%
12	76414	29	72.5%	14	35%
13	76410	25	62.5%	19	47.5%
14	76411	24	60%	16	40%
15	75566	22	55%	20	50%

Fig. 9.4: PSS Scale Scoring.

Out of 15 Patients, from Fig. 9.4, all the participants had significant and remarkable variations in their Scoring of PSS Scale - 10 that had been observed and recorded before and after the treatment. The Gradual decline in

scores is interpreted with efficacy of Mudra Therapy in the management of Stress. There is obvious amelioration in the mental health of the Participants with positive impact.

9.5 LEVEL OF STRESS BEFORE TREATMENT

Fig. 9.5: Level of Stress Before Treatment.

As shown in Fig. 9.5, Out of 15 study participants, there is no participant under the mild level of stress. 11 Participants come under moderate level of stress and 4

Participants come under severe level of stress at the time of Before Treatment.

9.6 LEVEL OF STRESS AFTER TREATMENT

Fig. 9.6: Level of Stress After Treatment.

As shown in Fig. 9.6, Out of 15 study participants, 5 Participants come under mild level of stress, 10 Participants come under moderate level of stress and No

Participants come under severe level of stress at the time of After Treatment.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

PAIRED T-TEST

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	BEFORE TREATMENT	24.53	15	3.226	0.833
	AFTER TREATMENT	17.93	15	3.262	0.842

Paired Samples Correlations					
			N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	BEFORE TREATMENT & AFTER TREATMENT		15	0.540	0.038

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	BEFORE TREATMENT - AFTER TREATMENT	6.600	3.112	0.804	4.877	8.323	8.213	14	0.000

H0 - There is no significant difference in Stress Score between before and after treatment.

Since the p value is <0.005 the H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted. Therefore Stress score is significantly decreased in before and after treatment.

Ha- There is significant difference in Stress Score between before and after treatment.

Paired Samples Effect Sizes						
		Standardizer ^a	Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval		
				Lower	Upper	
Pair 1	BEFORE TREATMENT - AFTER TREATMENT	Cohen's d	3.112	2.121	1.182	3.037
		Hedges' correction	3.199	2.063	1.150	2.955

a. denominator used in estimating the effect sizes
Cohen's *d* uses the sample standard deviation of the mean difference.

Hedges' correction uses the sample standard deviation of the mean difference, plus a correction factor.

9.7 MEAN ANALYSIS FROM STATISTICS

Fig. 9.7: Statistical Mean value.

As shown in Fig.9.7, there is significant decrease in mean value as observed in before treatment (24.53) and after treatment (17.93)

DISCUSSION

This Descriptive study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of Siddhar yogic Mudras had an influence in reducing the Stress Level. The clinical study was conducted with a well-defined protocol and a paper proforma after the approval of the Institutional Ethical Committee. 15 cases were related for induction to the trial. Before enrolment into the trial the informed consent was obtained from the patients. The patients were treated with Siddhar yogic mudras (Hand Gesture) once a day, This mudra treatment further follow up for 45 days in each participant and then participants prognosis are reported.

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of Siddhar yogic mudras (Hand Gesture) for Stress Management. This study was conducted in 15 participants, in this there are 47% of Male and 53% of Female.

Out of 15 participants, 26% of participants are in Below 20 years, 60% of participants are in 20- 30years, 7% of cases are in 30-40 years, 7% cases are in 40-50 years.

Out of 15 participants, about 20% are daily wages, 13% are House wife and 67% are Students.

As shown in Fig.9.7, there is significant decrease in mean value as observed in before treatment (24.53) and

after treatment (17.93). The *p* value is <0.005 the *H*₀ is rejected and *H*_a is accepted. Therefore Stress score is significantly decreased in before and after treatment.

CONCLUSION

The study results showed that 40% Good improvement, 27% had Moderate improvement, 33% had Mild improvement.

The study concludes that the Mudra Therapy is clinically effective in significant reduction and management of stress. Thus, efficacy of Mudra Therapy manipulation in the treatment of Stress is acknowledged. Most of the participants were of the opinion that yoga could help improve the overall health, both mental and physical, of an individual and they showed a positive response for willingness to recommend yoga to the general population to improve general health. So further to evaluate the Study to improve the Mental health through the Meditation and Mudra treatment (Hand Gesture).

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